

Research paper

Development of high-performance and cost-effective electrode assembly for redox flow batteries

Přemysl Richtr^a

^a University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Department of Chemical Engineering, Technická 5, 16628 Prague, Czech Republic

^b Fraunhofer Institute for Chemical Technology ICT, Department of Applied Electrochemistry, Joseph-von-Fraunhofer-Straße 7, 76327 Pfinztal, Germany

^c Pinflow energy storage, s.r.o. – Křižovnická 86/6, 11000 Prague, Czech Republic

^d Fraunhofer Institute for Chemical Technology ICT, Department of Polymer Engineering, Joseph-von-Fraunhofer-Straße 7, 76327 Pfinztal, Germany

^e BH Consulting Ltd., 4A Richardsson Rd, Coogee, WA, 6166 Australia

^f New Technologies – Research Centre, University of West Bohemia, Univerzitní 8, 30614, Plzeň, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Carbon-polymer composite plates
Welded electrode assemblies
Microwave welding
Hot-press welding
Vanadium redox flow battery

ABSTRACT

Redox flow batteries (RFBs) offer promising solutions for safe and durable stationary energy storage; however, high capital expenditures (CAPEX) hinder their commercialization. We developed a method for low-contact resistance welding of carbon-polymer composite plates to graphite felt electrodes and copper current collectors. Using our own extruded carbon-polymer composite plate with low carbon filling, we optimized two manufacturing methods: traditional hot-press and novel microwave welding. Electrode assembly samples were characterized by dry electric resistance measurements at compression ratios (*CR*) of 5–45 %, complex microstructural analysis via X-ray micro-computed tomography and scanning electron microscopy, and electrochemical characterization in a lab-scale vanadium RFB using voltammetry techniques, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, and galvanostatic charge-discharge cycling both in a single-cell and two-cell stacks. Hot-press welding significantly improved overall battery performance by reducing contact resistance up to 2.5 times compared to non-welded assemblies. At 10 % *CR*, the performance of developed assemblies matched commercial unbonded materials at 20 % *CR*, using a carbon-polymer composite plate with higher conductive filler content. Achieved stack parameters included area-specific resistance of 2.1 Ω cm² per cell and energy efficiency of 86.9 % at 40 mA cm⁻². Developed electrode assemblies remained stable after 800 cycles. Microwave welding enabled faster production of electrode assemblies with similar performance to hot-press welded ones. The developed electrode assemblies, based on low-filled carbon-polymer composite plate may substantially reduce battery stack costs and assembly complexity, leading to lower levelized cost of storage and more reproducible RFB fabrication.

1. Introduction

Increased use of renewable energy is essential to achieve the aimed carbon neutrality (EU goal for 2050) [1]. Due to the intermittent nature of photovoltaics and wind turbines, high-capacity energy storage technology is necessary to increase the share of these sources in the energy mix while securing safety and reliability of the energy supplies [2]. Various energy storage technologies are currently being used for these tasks, incl. pumped-hydroelectricity energy storage (PHES), hydrogen production and storage, or conventional batteries (such as Li-ion and

lead-acid cells) [3]. The installed world capacity of stationary energy storage in 2021 was 192 GW, with >90 % based on PHES and 7.5 % using batteries. Flow batteries of various chemistries accounted for only 1 % [4]. Li-ion batteries thus play a crucial role among the battery-based systems (sharing 90 % of the total installed battery capacity) due to their high efficiency and energy density. Remaining issues include fast capacity decay and high price resulting in high levelized costs of storage (LCOS) (0.25 \$/kWh/cycle [5]). Furthermore, Li-ion batteries use organic solvent-based electrolytes, making them extremely flammable. This motivates the development of alternative battery technologies

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: mazurp@vscht.cz (P. Mazúr).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2025.106285>

Received 10 June 2025; Received in revised form 8 July 2025; Accepted 12 July 2025

Available online 15 July 2025

2590-1230/© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

using aqueous electrolytes, incl. flow batteries, which provides a valuable additional feature of decoupled power and capacity. The most widely deployed flow battery type is based on vanadium aqueous electrolytes. The so-called all-vanadium redox flow battery (VRFB) excels in long lifetime (up to 15 000 cycles over 20 years) [6,7]. This is enabled by using a single redox active element providing four different oxidation states on negative (V^{2+}/V^{3+}) and positive side (VO^{2+}/VO_2^+) of the battery cell, preventing capacity fades due to a cross-contamination of the electrolytes [8–11].

A typical VRFB single-cell is outlined in Fig. 1. It consists of pairs of end plates, current collectors, bipolar plates (BP), and graphite felt (GF) electrodes, which are sandwiched on both sides of the separator. Ion-exchange membrane is typically used to hydraulically and electronically separate the respective half-cells (minimizing the vanadium ions cross-over, which is the main mechanism of recoverable capacity fade in VRFB [12]), while allowing for the ionic connection between the half-cells.

All parts of the battery must meet long-term chemical stability in the aggressive environment of the battery. Despite various types of BP reported [13], current industrial VRFB stacks are typically manufactured from composite materials composed of a suitable chemically stable polymeric binder and conductive carbon-based fillers. Carbon fillers provide sufficient electronic conductivity required for low battery resistance, while polymer binder enhances mechanical and processing properties, which makes these composites lighter, less brittle, and cheaper when compared to pure graphite plates. Additionally, high-surface-area carbon materials, such as carbon blacks or nanotubes, can be added to further enhance the electronic conductivity of the material and moreover optimal content of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) leads to the improved mechanical stability [14]. In general, various thermoplastic or thermosetting polymeric binders can be used, however, the choice is governed by chemical stability requirements of a specific RFB chemistry, which has a direct impact on the material properties and price. For VRFB stacks, typically polypropylene (PP), polyethylene (PE), or poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) binders are commonly used [15, 16]. Thermoplastic BPs can be produced by various processing technologies, incl. compression moulding, extrusion, or injection moulding [17].

Due to their suitable properties and relatively low price, GFs are mostly used as 3D electrodes in RFB stacks. They are industrially produced by graphitization of highly porous polymeric felts. They provide relatively high electric conductivity, high surface area available for electrochemical reactions and suitable textural properties to serve also as a flow distribution element [18]. For the application in aqueous RFBs, the felt activation is typically required to improve their wettability and to functionalize their surface by oxygen-containing functional groups, thus improving their electrocatalytic activity. The activation is typically done by thermal treatment in the presence of air [18,19], although several alternative methods have been reported, incl. chemical or

electrochemical oxidation [20–23]. Even for a given electrochemical reaction, the optimal activation conditions (temperature, time) were found to depend on many parameters such as the condition of graphitization, choice of felt precursors (rayon or polyacrylonitrile), presence of impurities, etc. [24,25]. In case of VRFB, the activation has a major influence preferentially on negative electrode performance [19], both in terms of initial performance and durability [8]. Alternatively, the GF catalytic activity and hydrophobicity can be enhanced by the application of Sr-based perovskite nanoparticles to the surface [26].

Electronic conductivity of current collectors, BPs, GF, and ionic conductivity of membrane and electrolytes contribute to the inner ohmic area specific resistance of the cell (ASR_{Ω}). Depending on the parameters of the used cell components, ASR_{Ω} ranges from 52 % up to 82 % of overall VRFB cell resistance [27,28] and thus has a significant influence on the energy efficiency (EE) of the battery charge-discharge cycle. Minimization of ASR_{Ω} enables efficient battery operation at high current densities, which, in turn, decreases the stack size for the required power output, making the battery more economically competitive [17,29,30].

ASR_{Ω} can be reduced by increasing the compression rate (CR) of the GF, which enhances GF through-plane conductivity and, more importantly, reduces contact resistances between individual electronically conductive components, particularly between GF and BP. Increased compression of GF, however, in the same time lowers their porosity and permeability for the electrolyte flow, which decreases the overall efficiency of the system due to increased pumping losses. These effects have been reported in several studies [28,31–33]. In our previous study, Charvát et al. [28] systematically studied the effect of GF compression on cell resistance and pumping losses; the optimal CR was identified as a minimum of total power losses, incl. both pumping and cell polarization losses. This optimum was found to be significantly dependent on the felt properties (porosity, precursor polymer), which emphasizes the need for proprietary optimization of the cell geometry for the selected active components.

Besides increased compression, several more efficient strategies have been reported for decrease of GF-BP contact resistance without negative impact on GF permeability [34,35], such as use of: adhesive conducting layer (ACL) between GF and BP [36], integrating BP into the structure of GF with assistance of soluble resins [34,37] and thermal laminating/hot-pressing of the components [38]. The integration of GFs and BP into a single electrode assembly, besides decreasing the contact resistance, also reduces the number of components used during the battery stack assembly, thus minimizing the assembly errors and workload.

ACL is a thin graphite-polymeric composite layer with a bulk resistivity lower than that of the carbon-based bipolar plate. It typically consists of a mixture of carbon particles (e.g. graphite flakes or fibres) and polymeric binder coated onto the BP surfaces, which significantly reduces the GF-BP contact resistance due to intensified contact between both conductive components at the modified interface. Cao et al. [36] successfully demonstrated preparation of the electrode assembly via use of ACL (middle stack cell electrode, GF/BP/GF), which led to EE growth by 4.1 % (to 79.8 % at 150 mA cm^{-2}) when compared to the conventional stack assembly of iron-chromium RFB. Integrating bipolar plate within the GF structure (end cell electrode assembly) was reported [34], a similar principle was used for the preparation of the middle stack cell electrode assembly [37]. In both cases, the contact resistance was decreased and EE increased by 7.65 % (to 85.8 % at 100 mA cm^{-2}) and 4.85 % (to 81.9 % at 100 mA cm^{-2}), respectively.

Both mentioned methods integrate an additional layer within a GF-BP assembly in order to effectively decrease the contact resistance. In contrast, thermal bonding (further in the text referred to as welding) of GF to BP seems to be a more promising approach as no additional layer is needed. Instead, via a careful heating of compressed BP-GF assembly, some of the felt fibres can penetrate through a partially melted thermoplastic binder within a surface region of BP which provides a

Fig. 1. Schematic of the inner design of a single-cell of a redox flow battery. Provided and shown with agreement of Pinflow Energy Storage, s.r.o.

connection of both components after subsequent cooling. The contact resistance is decreased due to increased interfacial area between the fibres and filler particles. Besides the decreased contact resistance, the welding also enables reduction of the number of components used within the stack assembly, which results in a simpler, more precise and cheaper stack production.

The use of hot-press welding (HPW) method was reported in [38], where the optimized welding parameters (applied pressure, time and temperature) provided 2 % *EE* increase (to 84 %) when compared to conventional assembly. To the best of our knowledge, this is the only study that employs direct hot-press welding (without ACL) for the BP and GF together. Unfortunately, this study lacks detailed electrochemical characterization and experimental conditions are very vaguely specified.

At the terminal electrodes of a battery stack, BPs are in a direct contact with the respective current collectors (typically copper plates) where another contact resistance is present. Although this CC-BP contact resistance is present only on the terminal electrodes, it still contributes to the overall ASR_{Ω} of the battery stack. Moreover, the role of CC is to homogeneously distribute the current within the entire electrode area, and thus a homogeneity of CC-BP connection is of high importance. Choe and Lim [39] used HPW (2 h, 125 °C) to connect a copper current collector with a BP modified with an inserted carbon/epoxy prepreg layer, increasing *EE* of VRFB single-cell by 4.1 % (to 82.4 % at 100 mA cm^{-2}), when compared to the conventional configuration.

In most of the mentioned studies, as well as in most industrial RFB stacks, low ASR_{Ω} at acceptable CRs (i.e., pumping losses) is achieved by the use of highly conductive BPs with high filler content, which are typically produced by a costly compression-moulding process. In contrast, extruded BPs with decreased carbon content offer several benefits: production in a cost-effective, scalable process is suitable for a continuous production; higher binder content improves mechanical properties of the plates and simplifies its welding to other cell components (GF or CC) without the need of the additional agent (such as ACL). However, generally lower carbon content required for the extrudability increases ASR_{Ω} of the cell, particularly due to increased contact GF-BP resistances (due to a lower share of conductive region within a BP surface). The possibility of continuous production is the key parameter for the price reduction. Moreover, cost and performance cannot be separated, i.e. the real cost that must always be considered is the LCOS.

Thus, within our study, we focused on the development of the cost-effective electrode assemblies by welding GF and CC to our developed extruded BPs to mitigate the contact resistances between the components. The study is divided into three parts describing: i) production of extruded bipolar plates (BP_{ext.}) with a rich polymeric assay, ii) optimization of HPW and novel MWW methods for the bonding of developed BPs with the other cell components (2 different GFs and 2 different CC materials were used to prepare 3 types of electrode assemblies: GF/BP_{ext.}, CC/BP_{ext.}/GF and GF/BP_{ext.}/GF); iii) complex characterization of the prepared assemblies incl. dry electric resistance measurement, microstructure analysis and VRFB single-cell and multi-cell stack testing using a complex electrochemical characterization protocol. For the first time, the use of both terminal (including integrated CC) and bipolar electrode assemblies was demonstrated within a VRFB stack, achieving performance parameters comparable to a conventional electrode assembly. With the welding conditions optimized for the individual electrode assemblies, we achieved significant performance enhancement of the battery operation with the potential of decreased production costs of VRFB stacks.}}

2. Experimental

2.1. Production of extruded bipolar plate

For the preparation of the extrudable BPs (patented by Fraunhofer ICT [40]), polypropylene (Moplen HP500N) was selected as the

polymeric matrix and carbon nanotubes (CNT, Cabot) and expanded graphite flakes (4 mm particle size, Frenzelit, sheet-like graphite flakes from expanded graphite foil) were selected as graphitic fillers. In the first step, a master batch with a CNT content of 6.98 wt. % in the PP matrix was produced in the compounding process. In the second step, graphite flakes filler was added, and the final proportions were adjusted according to Table 1. Several factors had to be weighed against each other: PP content of approx. 25 wt. % to ensure weldability of the BP material and the highest possible filling level of conductive components for sufficiently high conductivity. At the same time, the processing properties of the materials must be taken into account, which, based on our experience, can limit the manufacturing processes as the filler content increases. The compounding was done on a Leistritz 27D twin screw extruder in most cases with 10 kg/h production rate, rotation frequency of 800 RPM and 200 °C. The optimal compound composition was as follows: 57 wt. % of expanded graphite flakes, 3 wt. % of CNTs and 40 wt. % of PP.

BPs with a thickness of 1.0 mm were produced under the optimized conditions by sheet roll (hot) extrusion at the Fraunhofer Institute for Process Engineering and Packaging IVV in Freising, Germany. Relevant parameters of the extruded BP (BP_{ext.}) and commercial BP (BP_{com.}, PPG 86 Eisenhuth) are compared in Table 1. We can see that the developed BP_{ext.} has 10 times lower through-plane conductivity due to the rich polymeric assay. The higher content of PP enables the production of thinner BP, which partially compensates for the lower conductivity. Moreover, the developed BP is more flexible and lighter and, most importantly, weldable. The mechanical properties of the extruded bipolar plates (BP_{ext.}) were measured according to the method described by Hala et al. [41], while the mechanical properties of the commercial BP_{com.} were obtained from the manufacturer's datasheet [42]. The BP_{ext.} exhibits higher flexural strength (by approx. 50 %) and lower bending modulus (approx. half to BP_{com.}), indicating improved mechanical durability and flexibility.

2.2. Manufacture and materials for electrode assemblies

Three different electrode assemblies were developed: GF/BP_{ext.}, CC/BP_{ext.}/GF and GF/BP_{ext.}/GF (see Fig. 2 and Table 2). For the CC/BP_{ext.}/GF assembly, two different Cu-based CC materials were used: copper foil (0.11 mm thick) and copper plate (2.0 mm thick). Two different GFs based on polyacrylonitrile (PAN) precursor were used within the study, the list of their relevant parameters is summarized in Table 3. The GF1 was provided already activated by the producer and, therefore, it was used as received. The GF₂ was thermally activated in our lab by the following procedure: a felt sample was placed in a preheated furnace (at 400 °C) without inner air circulation and left there for 1 hour and then taken out. A polymeric-rich skin layer was removed from the BP_{ext.} surface with sandpaper (grit size 1200), followed by cleaning of the surface with propan-2-ol. Two different manufacturing approaches were carried out: hot-press welding and microwave welding.}}}

2.2.1. Hot-press welding (HPW)

First method used a pneumatic press with heated plates (both top and bottom plates, power output up to 3 kW each), cooling water was pumped through the plates to avoid exceeding the set temperature. Aluminium distance frame with a square hole for the GF sample was used to secure the defined compression of GF (in a 15–30 % CR range) and to allow sufficient heat transfer from the heating plates to the BP_{ext.}, as well as to prevent bending of the BP_{ext.} during HPW.

The electrode assembly parts (for schematic of set-ups for hot-pressing see Fig. 3a-c) were placed into the pre-heated hot-press and a pressure of 3.2 kPa (for CR of 15 %) was applied for a required time. Thin PTFE foils (0.08 mm) were used to protect BP from direct contact with the surface of the heating plates. Different temperatures (ranging from 170–215 °C), distance frame thickness and times of heating and cooling were tested within the HPW optimization with mostly visual

Table 1

Relevant parameters of BP_{ext.} and BP_{com.} used as a reference (according to [15]). *Measured as a sandwich of two gold-plated copper plates at a defined pressure of 100 N cm⁻².

BP	Thickness mm	Graphite content wt. %	CNT content wt. %	Through plane conductivity S cm ⁻¹	Area specific resistance mΩ cm ²	Flexural strength MPa	Bending modulus MPa
BP _{com.}	2.0	86	–	5.5	12	30	8500
BP _{ext.}	1.0	57	3	0.56*	188*	47.5	4375

Fig. 2. All types of electrode assemblies manufactured in this work: a) GF/BP_{ext.}, b) CC/BP_{ext.}/GF and c) GF/BP_{ext.}/GF. Red lines show the position of the bonding interface between the components.

Table 2

List of the electrode assemblies prepared within this study and the components used for their manufacture.

assembly	CC	BP	GF	Welding process
GF/BP	–	BP _{ext.}	GF ₁ /GF ₂	hot-press
GF/BP	–	BP _{ext.}	GF ₂	microwave
CC/GF/BP	Cu foil	BP _{ext.}	GF ₁	hot-press
GF/BP/GF	–	BP _{ext.}	2 x GF ₁	hot-press

Table 3

GF materials used within this study and their relevant parameters.

	Producer	Type	Thickness /mm	Precursor	Activation
GF ₁	AvCarb	G475A	4.75	PAN	Commercial (as received)
GF ₂	Ceramaterials	GFE 1	6.0	PAN	1 hour, 400 °C, air

inspection of the bonding quality. The operational conditions (pressure, temperature, and welding time) have a very limited range due to the visible deformation of the carbon composite plate when conditions deviate slightly from the optimum. Lower temperatures fail to melt the polymer sufficiently, preventing proper connections. Increased pressure damages the graphite felt structure or the carbon composite plate, while lower pressure results in partial or no connection of the felt. Longer welding times at optimal temperatures cause the carbon composite plate to melt and flow. Lower temperatures combined with longer welding times are unsuitable for continuous fast production. Optimized process conditions (for GF/BP_{ext.}/GF and GF/BP_{ext.}) were identified as follows: 205 °C for 3 min, followed by cooling until reaching 175 °C, release of the pressure and removal of the electrode assembly and cooling out of the press. The whole process took approx. 20 min. In case of (CC/BP_{ext.}/GF), a slightly longer cooling phase in the press was necessary until the temperature decreased to 160 °C. To look more closely at the heat transport across the surface of the GF/BP_{ext.} interface during HPW, three

thermocouples (K-type 0.5 mm, RS PRO) were placed in different positions within the GF/BP/GF electrode assembly (schematically shown in Figure S1). Thermocouple 1 (T₁) was positioned on the surface of the GF (close to the heat source), T₂ was positioned at the edge of GF/BP_{ext.} interface and on the BP_{ext.} surface, T₃ was placed on the surface of the BP_{ext.} in the middle of the GF (both in terms of width and length). The data were collected using the Tevomet TV16 multichannel voltage and temperature monitor (Kolibrík.net).

2.2.2. Microwave welding (MWW)

For the MWW we used a specialized machine constructed by Fraunhofer ICT (for the schematics of the microwave see Fig. 3d). MWW was used only for the preparation of the GF/BP_{ext.} assembly. GF was placed in the distance frame (with cut area for the GF insertion, similar to HPW) made of polymeric felt with reduced thickness to achieve 15 % CR. The BP_{ext.} was laid on top of the felt and covered by a polymeric foil, which created an airtight space for assembly compression by a vacuum pump for effective bonding of the components in the assembly. The generated microwaves (2.45 GHz frequency) were passed through a waveguide tube and directed to the welded sample by the probe. The probe with approx. width of 2.2 cm was moved above the sample with a speed of 1 mm s⁻¹ (CNC movement in y-axis, in x and z-axis it was moved manually), power output was max. 350 W for the heating and about 170 W power for holding the temperature on top of the polymeric foil at 160 °C. The temperature on the surface was monitored by a thermal camera and based on the response, the power output was regulated. Microwaves were applied to a larger area (9 × 9 cm², 5 overlapping lanes driven) than was the GF area (7 × 7 cm²) to secure homogeneous temperature distribution within the bonding area and to have proper connection of the components even at the edges. The entire process took approx. 15 min, while welding itself took 7.5 min. The rest of the time was spent on manual movement of sample in x-axis, additional sample handling and approx. 30 s for the cooling down of the prepared electrode assembly.

2.3. Mechanical properties measurements

Three-point flexural bending characterization was carried out on TexturePro CT V1.7 build 28 (Brookfield Engineering Labs. Inc.) with TA7 probe (60 mm wide knife). Two types of tests were conducted: i) single loading until sample rupture to determine the maximum flexural strength and ii) cyclic loading under a constant force of 5 N (load range around 80–90 % of maximal load before sample rupture) for 300 cycles to evaluate mechanical durability of the BP/GF samples. The test specimens had a length of 60 mm, a width of 9 mm, and a thickness corresponding to the actual thickness of the characterized sample.

2.4. Microstructure analysis of electrode assemblies

Detailed microstructure of the selected developed electrode assemblies was studied by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and micro computed tomography (μCT, cylindrical sample with a diameter of 2 mm). For the latter, the samples were scanned using an X-ray microtomograph, Xradia 400. An accelerating voltage of 55 kV was used for scanning, and 2400 images were taken for each scan with a resolution of 1.091 μm/pixel and an exposure time of 6 s/image. The total scanning time was five hours. The resulting structure was obtained from the captured images by mathematical reconstruction in the native software

Fig. 3. Cross-sectional schematics of experimental set-ups for the electrode assemblies manufacture by: hot-press welding with individual components used (arrows indicate directions of heat flux and pressure): a) CC/BP_{ext.}/GF electrode assembly, b) GF/BP_{ext.}/GF electrode assembly, c) GF/BP_{ext.} electrode assembly. d) Cross-sectional schematics of experimental set-ups for the electrode assemblies manufacture by microwave welding (movement controlled by CNC in y-direction), low pressure used for setting the CR. The grey rectangle represents the frame from polymeric felt for setting the distance to set the required CR.

of the microtomograph.

To achieve the best possible resolution for SEM analysis, each sample was first cut from the bulk using a special punch and then cut and polished using a Leica EM FC cryo-ultramicrotome in an axis perpendicular to the fibre-BP interface. The sample was first roughly cut on a glass knife and then the surface was polished on a special diamond knife at a temperature of $-160\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Thanks to the low temperature, the binder polymer is not smeared during cutting and the fibres are not torn out of the structure. The samples pre-prepared using the microtome were characterized by SEM (TESCAN VEGA 3), specifically SEM-SE (always left side of the image) and SEM-BSE (always right side of the image). The representative part of the interface of the carbon felt with the bipolar plate was captured first perpendicular to the vertical cut of the component, then the majority of the felt was removed, and the interface was captured directly along the axis of the original cut. A working

distance of about 16 mm was used for the first view and about 11 mm for the second. In both cases, the high-voltage electron beam was set at 20 kV, magnification levels of 1380x and the view field at $500\text{ }\mu\text{m}$.

2.5. Dry resistance measurement

The dry resistance was measured for all the manufactured electrode assemblies (see Table 4). The apparatus (similar to the [28]) consisting of a tensile tester (press, Instron 5544), two insulating plates (made from polyvinylchloride (PVC) and two composite plates PPG 86 (Eisenhuth) is schematically shown in Figure S2. The resistance was measured in a four-point arrangement with a couple of current-sensing and a couple of voltage-sensing electrodes placed on opposite sides of the current collectors. The schematics of electrode assemblies and positions of sensing cables are shown in Figure S3. The measured resistance values were

Table 4

Electrode assemblies and references used for ASR_{dry} measurements. The sign “/” and “+” are used for bonded and unbonded components, respectively.

assembly	reference 1	reference 2
GF/BP	GF+BP _{com.}	
CC/BP/GF	CC+ BP _{com.} +GF	CC+GF/BP _{ext.}
GF/BP/GF	GF+ BP _{com.} + GF	GF+BP _{ext.} +GF

re-calculated to area specific resistance (referred to as dry area specific resistance, ASR_{dry} , assuming a 50 cm² active electrode area (i.e. area of GF electrode). ASR_{dry} were measured under GF compression in a CR range of 5–45 %.

The dry area specific of single-cell $ASR_{dry-cell}$ of RFB without membrane was measured to determine the share of ohmic resistance created by individual components. The construction of the cell is the same as in Figure S4a but the membrane was excluded. All the electrode assemblies that were tested in single-cell arrangement were characterized under chosen CR with respect to the electrochemical characterization (detailed description in **chapter 2.6**). $ASR_{dry-cell}$ was evaluated from the slope of the dynamic load curve measured in a 0–80 mA cm⁻² current density range by linear fitting.

2.6. Construction of the flow cell and general conditions

The prepared electrode assemblies were finally tested in a VRFB, using a single-cell and a two-cell battery stack. In Figure S4a, the schematics of the flow cell are shown (Pinflow Energy Storage s.r.o.). It consists of aluminium end plates, CC, BP, GF, elastomeric polyolefin-based flat gaskets, electrolyte distribution frames made of PVC, anion-exchange membrane FAP 450 (Fumatech) assembled in a dry state as received. PPG 86 (Eisenhuth) was used as a reference BP material, to compare battery performance with the manufactured electrode assemblies using the developed BP_{ext.}. The reference VRFB with unbonded GFs has 20 % CR, while the VRFB with the developed electrode assemblies has only 10 % CR. The geometric area of the electrodes was 50 cm² (7.07 × 7.07 cm²). Flow-through distribution of electrolyte was used for both half-cell compartments.

The apparatus (see Figure S4b, c) for the testing of the prepared electrode assemblies under the VRFB conditions consisted of a flow cell or stack, diaphragm pump used for the single-cell experiments (KNF) or a peristaltic pump for the stack experiments (Watson–Marlow 323), two separate electrolyte tanks and PTFE tubing connecting the tanks to the cell/stack. Electrolyte tanks were connected to a nitrogen supply to prevent any oxidation of electrolyte species by atmospheric oxygen. The OCV cell (Pinflow Energy Storage s.r.o.), containing PPG 86 carbon-polymer composite electrodes (Eisenhuth) and FAP 450 membrane (Fumatech) was positioned at the inlet of the main cell to monitor the battery state of charge (SoC) during the entire experiment. Each tank contained 0.07 dm³ of 1.6 mol dm⁻³ vanadium electrolyte (initially equimolar mixture solution of V³⁺/VO²⁺ ions), 2 mol dm⁻³ of H₂SO₄ and 0.3 wt. % of H₃PO₄. The flow rate of both electrolytes was set to 75 ml min⁻¹. In case of the stack experiments, the volume of electrolyte was 0.105 dm³ and the flow rate was double, i.e. 150 ml min⁻¹. The experiments were carried out at room temperature, that was controlled by air conditioning to approx. 22 °C.

2.7. Electrochemical characterization of VRFB

For the characterization of the electrode assemblies in a VRFB single-cell we used a complex procedure consisting of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) using Zahner IM6e (Zahner) and dynamic load curves (LC) and galvanostatic cycling using BasyTec GMS (BasyTec GmbH). For the stack characterization, different devices were used: for EIS we used potentiostat BSC-815 (Biologic) and for LC and galvanostatic cycling measurements we used potentiostat PTC-520E in

combination with Tevomet TV16 multichannel voltage monitor (both Kolibri.net) which enabled voltage monitoring of individual cells during the entire experiment.

In both configurations, the battery was first characterized by EIS at –50 % SoC. EIS was measured at OCV in a potentiostatic mode in the frequency range from 100 kHz (for the stack measurements from 10 kHz) to 50 mHz with a sinus amplitude of the perturbing signal of 20 mV. Subsequently, the battery was galvanostatically charged to the theoretical +50 % SoC at a current density of 40 mA cm⁻². At this SoC, EIS (same settings as in –50 % SOC) and a dynamic LC characterization were performed. The LC measurement was performed by a dynamic current density increase in a range of 0 ± 60 mA cm⁻² with a linear increase of 1 mA cm⁻² s⁻¹. Subsequently, galvanostatic charge-discharge cycling of the battery was performed at 40 mA cm⁻² in a 0.8 - 1.65 V voltage range (stack cycling in 1.6 - 3.3 V range). The last cycle was ended by potentiostatic discharge at 0.8 V (1.6 V for stack measurement) until the current density drops below 10 % of the discharging current density (i.e. below 4 mA cm⁻²). After the cycling, the electrolytes from both tanks were mixed and split to equal volumes, in order to restore the initial electrolyte composition, and the characterization in –50 % SoC (EIS) and +50 % SoC (EIS+LC) was repeated. To ensure consistency, we have performed repeated measurements with selected electrode assemblies GF/BP_{ext.} and CC/BP_{ext.}/GF in VRFB single-cell. Repeated measurements were performed only for selected electrode assemblies due to the complexity and time-intensive nature of the experiments.

A long-term experiment was conducted to assess the stability of electrode assemblies (with terminal electrode assembly CC/BP_{ext.}/GF₂ and middle electrode assembly GF₂/BP_{ext.}/GF₂), under accelerated conditions. When compared to the std. experiment conditions, the current density was increased to 80 mA cm⁻² and the vanadium electrolyte volume was 0.1 dm³ of 1.6 mol dm⁻³. The experiment was conducted on the potentiostat VSP-3e (Biologic). The experimental apparatus was inside the temperature-controlled box at a given temperature of 20 °C. Dynamic LC characterization was performed in a current density range of 0 ± 100 mA cm⁻². The rest of the working conditions remained the same.

From the EIS experiments, the values of ASRs were evaluated; the ohmic ASR (ASR_{Ω}), charge transfer ASR (ASR_{CT}) and total ASR ($ASR_{tot-EIS}$) by fitting the EIS spectra to a suitable equivalent circuit model (for equivalent circuit, see Figure S5). The charging and discharging area specific resistances (ASR_{LC-ch} , ASR_{LC-d}) were evaluated from the slope of the linear part of the corresponding LCs (current density region of 0 - 60 mA cm⁻²). In case of VRFB stack measurements, all the parameters were evaluated for the entire stack as well as for individual cells separately. The characterization was performed at the beginning (initial, INT) of the experiment and after (after, AFT). From the galvanostatic charge-discharge cycling, the coulombic and energy efficiency (CE and EE , respectively) and capacity utilization (CU) were evaluated according to std. relations [19] together with their mean values from 10 cycles. CU was calculated with respect to the theoretical capacity of the electrolytes according to Faraday's law.

3. Results

The primary aim of this study was to optimize the method for the manufacture of highly efficient electrode assemblies with the connection of GF, BP, and CC. The result section is divided into two parts: The first part focuses on the manufacturing process of the electrode assemblies by both studied methods, including detailed microstructural analysis, while the second part presents the results of electrical and electrochemical characterization results of the electrodes in both single-cell and 2-cells stack of VRFB.

3.1. Manufacture of electrode assemblies

3.1.1. GF/BP_{ext.} and GF/BP_{ext.}/GF electrode assembly manufacture

Hot-press welding (HPW)

Based on previous research, we experienced that BP_{com.} with high carbon filling cannot be used for heat bonding with GF due to its low polymer binder content (only 15 wt. % in the case of PPG86, Eisenhuth). Thus, the developed BP_{ext.} were tested for HPW and the process parameters were optimized for the GF/BP_{ext.} assembly and further adopted also for GF/BP_{ext.}/GF assembly. The optimal temperature range for HPW of GF to BP_{ext.} was found to be 190–205 °C. Using lower temperatures either takes too long or does not provide sufficient connection. Using higher temperatures requires longer cooling times and causes damage, particularly due to the excessive BP_{ext.} melting and its penetration to the GF structure at the edge of GF/BP_{ext.} contact area (not all over the GF/BP_{ext.} interface). This type of damage occurs on both the top and bottom sides of BP_{ext.} where in contact with GF (see Figure S6).

Minimal CR of GF during the HPW was set to 15 % in order to secure sufficient contact between the components. At higher CRs, the residues of carbon fibres from the disintegrated GF appeared on the PTFE foil after the manufacturing process, which indicates GF damage. Due to high pressure or high temperature, the changes in BP_{ext.} thickness appeared, caused by excessive melting of the polymeric matrix. Thus, the optimal conditions range of the HPW process was found out to be relatively narrow. The duration of the cooling phase (reaching the chosen temperature before removing the assembly from the press) was found to be a crucial parameter, significantly affecting the quality of the bonded GF/BP_{ext.} assembly. Removing the assembly before it was cooled down to 175 °C caused increased surface roughness and bending of BP_{ext.} (see Fig. 4a, b). Moreover, we observed a deformed BP_{ext.} surface in the area of the connected GF, when compared to the rest of the plate.

This damage could lead to electrolyte leakage from the VRFB stack and compromise the mechanical integrity of BP. The GF/BP_{ext.}/GF electrode assembly was manufactured under the same conditions as the GF/BP_{ext.} but using two distance frames (each for the individual felt).

Temperature profiles during HPW are captioned in Fig. 4d. At the beginning, the temperature rose quickly as the assembly was inserted into the press. After 180 s, the heat source was turned off and the assembly began to spontaneously cool down, still under applied pressure (cooling phase). After approximately 900 s, the temperature reached 175 °C and the assembly was released from the press. After 1000 s, the thermocouples were removed. We can see that the temperature measured by T₁ (thermocouple located on the outer surface of the felt closer to the heat source) rises more quickly during the heating phase and cools down more slowly during the cooling phase. The T₂ and T₃ thermocouples were positioned to the surface of BP, T₃ in the middle of the felt (in terms of width and length, not depth), while T₂ on the edge of the GF/BP_{ext.} interface (see Figure S1b). For T₂ and T₃, the time to reach a steady state was about 40 s longer than T₁ because of the thermal insulation effect of GF. Thermal insulation property can negatively influence the HPW process for increased electrode area, where the heat transport limitations from a distance frame to the middle of the electrode assembly can result in non-homogeneous temperature distribution within the heat-bonded interface. For our sample dimension, aluminium distance frames sufficiently facilitated the heat transport, but in a real-scale production, with ten times larger electrode areas, this potential issue must be addressed correspondingly.

Microwave welding (MWW)

Alternatively, a different manufacturing process of microwave welding (MWW) was used for the manufacture of GF/BP_{ext.} electrode assembly. The distance frame from the polymeric felt of defined thickness was used to achieve the required GF compression of 15 %, which

Fig. 4. Images of the prepared GF/BP_{ext.} electrode assembly illustrating: a) deformation of BP_{ext.} on the GF side due to insufficient length of cooling phase, b) deformation of BP_{ext.} on CC side due to insufficient length of cooling phase, c) undeformed GF/BP_{ext.} electrode assembly under optimal conditions. d) Temperature profile during HPW, thermocouples position specified in Section 2.2.

was crucial for creating a homogeneous connection across the entire GF/BP_{ext.} electrode assembly. If the thickness was not optimal, we observed depressions or projections at the connection area (similarly to Figure S6b, c), although the connection is still created in both cases. With the optimal CR, the GF/BP_{ext.} assembly had a smooth surface, and the cooling times were very fast. The assembly could be handled in less than a minute after the welding, which is much faster compared to the HPW method. The manufacturing process took about 15 min, but it could be significantly shortened with complete CNC control of the welding machine and by adding more microwave probes to cover the entire active area. MWW is potentially also more suitable for roll-to-roll process implementation on an industrial scale. Unfortunately, the manufacturing of GF/BP_{ext.}/GF nor CC/BP_{ext.}/GF assemblies was impossible with the MWW machine available for our study. The MWW can also be used only for limited types of materials, for example metals opaque to the micro-waves and even the GF can partially absorb them [43], which might disable the bonding of CC. Overall, the MWW method seems very promising for the fast production of BP/GF electrode assemblies for RFB stacks.

A comparison of mechanical properties of developed BP/GF assemblies between the two manufacturing processes was conducted (see Table 5). The results indicate that bonding of GF to the BP by both methods (HPW and MWW) reduce the flexural strength of the electrode assembly compared to the unmodified BP_{ext.}. While MWW appears to have a more pronounced negative effect, this may be attributed to the slightly higher flexural strength observed in the one of HPW sample, which resulted in a higher standard deviation and may have influenced the comparison. Reduction of flexural strength of electrode assemblies may be attributed to the presence of the welded GF, which introduces additional mechanical resistance and partially restricts bending, potentially leading to earlier onset of the composite plate rupture.

However, it is important to note that in a real battery stack, mechanical deformation of BP is partially reduced by the compressibility of adjacent GFs. This compression is expected to absorb part of the mechanical stress, thereby reducing the likelihood of significant BP bending or its failure. Furthermore, despite the observed reduction, the flexural strength of the welded electrode assemblies remains higher than that of the conventionally moulded bipolar plate BP_{com.}, indicating that the mechanical integrity of the extruded and welded configuration is still sufficient for practical application.

To further assess the mechanical stability of the electrode assemblies, a cyclic flexural load test was performed. Over the course of 300 cycles, no significant degradation in flexural strength was observed. Only one MWW sample exhibited cracking after 84 cycles. Overall, the flexural strength remained comparable between the two welding methods under identical loading conditions, suggesting good mechanical durability of the welded assemblies.

3.1.2. CC/BP_{ext.}/GF electrode assembly manufacture by hot-press welding

Different strategies were tested to optimize the CC/BP_{ext.}/GF assembly by HPW. The stepwise methods, either connecting CC and BP_{ext.} first and then bonding with GF or connecting BP_{ext.} and GF first and then bonding with CC, were unsuccessful. The first method led to partial disconnection of CC from BP_{ext.} during the second step, the second method negatively affected the quality of the GF/BP_{ext.} connection. The best approach was to connect all three components in a single step.

Two different CC materials were tested - copper plate (2.0 mm thick) and copper foil (0.11 mm thick). Similarly, to the GF/BP_{ext.} assembly, the cooling phase significantly impacted the quality of the CC-BP_{ext.}

Table 5
Mechanical properties of electrode assemblies.

	HPW	MWW	BP _{ext.}
Flexural strength	45.06±3.61	42.98±0.03	47.49±0.61
Flexural strength (cyclic)	35.95±0.11	35.94±0.03	

connection. The cooling phase needed to be extended, with a lower termination temperature of 160 °C, to prevent disconnection of CC due to the tension between CC and BP_{ext.}, most probably caused by the different heat transport rates of the materials (thermal conductivity of copper used for CC and BP is 400 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹ and 15 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹, respectively) [44]. This issue was more pronounced with the thicker CC copper plate, the connection with the copper foil was better (based on visual observations). The thickness of the copper foil was still sufficient for the homogeneous current distribution during electrochemical characterization. For more details see Figure S7.

3.1.3. Microstructural analysis of prepared electrode assemblies

Top view on the GF/BP_{ext.} interface of the MWW and HPW electrode assembly shows that GF fibres are embedded within the BP_{ext.} structure (see Fig. 5a, b) even after mechanical ripping the upper part of GF (for the sake of the SEM image). There is no clear difference between the HPW and MWW bonding methods. Similarly, the side view reveals no noticeable differences in the BP_{ext.} structure (see Figure S12).

Second visualization of the contact between the conductive fillers of the BP_{ext.} and GF fibres can be seen from the μ CT scans (see Fig. 5e, f). The blue arrows in the μ CT scan show direct contacts of GF fibres with conductive fillers of BP_{ext.}, within the region of the GF/BP interface. This clearly demonstrates the presence of contact points between conductive phases of both components within the assembly, which significantly reduce the contact resistance between the components. Additionally, μ CT scans were reconstructed to visualize a GF/BP interface (see Figure S13), only showing the conductive parts of this electrode assembly. In the reconstruction, GF fibers are shown in blue, while the conductive parts of the BP (i.e., graphite particles) are shown in yellow. This detailed reconstruction confirms that numerous contacts between the conductive phases are present throughout the sample area.

3.1.4. Dry resistance measurements

The ASR_{dry} of GF/BP_{ext.} electrode assembly Fig. 6a, (for schemes of the assemblies and sensing cables connection see Figure S3) was measured under GF compression in the CR range of 5–45 % in two different setups: GF+BP_{com.} (the sing “+” stand for unbonded assembly) and a GF/BP_{ext.} electrode assembly (BP_{ext.} with polymeric skin layer removed with sandpaper, GF bonded by HPW). From the figures, we can see that the bonding of the GF reduces the contact resistance of GF-BP_{ext.} interface, particularly at low CRs (up to 35 %), providing even lower ASR_{dry} when compared to the commercial BP. The ASR_{dry} of GF/BP_{ext.} at 10 % CR is thus equivalent to GF+BP_{com.} at 20 % CR, which enables to use of GF electrodes at lower CR (and thus with lower pumping energy losses). These CR values were also used in the subsequent VRFB tests.

In Fig. 6b, we present the results of ASR_{dry} measurements for GF/BP_{ext.}/GF, GF+BP_{com.}+GF (commercial reference) and GF+BP_{ext.}+GF (developed unbonded) electrode assemblies. The positive effect of heat bonding of GFs on the reduction of the BP-GF contact resistance is evident from the comparison of GF/BP/GF with GF+BP_{ext.}+GF, the unbonded assembly provides significantly higher ASR_{dry} in the entire CRs range. At CRs below 25 %, ASR_{dry} of the bonded assembly is even lower than for the unbonded assembly based on commercial BP. Thus, even though the developed BP_{ext.} with lower assay of conductive fillers has one order of magnitude lower electric conductivity (see Table 1, Section 2.1), by heat-bonding them with the GFs and CC, the ASR_{dry} of the resulting electrode assemblies can be comparable or even lower than for the unbonded assemblies using more conductive commercial BP material with higher content of the fillers (by 26 %).

A similar comparison is shown in Fig. 6c for the manufactured CC/BP/GF assembly and two reference electrode assemblies: CC+BP_{com.}+GF and CC+GF/BP_{ext.}. The ASR_{dry} of the CC/BP_{ext.}/GF is significantly lower at low CRs compared to the commercial assembly, which is caused by the reduction of the CC-BP contact resistance. Less flat surface of the BP_{ext.} for GF/BP_{ext.} assembly, when compared to the BP_{com.}, and thus higher CC-BP contact resistance is mostly responsible

Fig. 5. SEM of top view of the interface of $BP_{ext.}$ and welded (GF) after ripping off the upper part of the GF for a) fresh MWW, b) fresh HPW and c) used HPW electrode assembly. Corresponding images from μ CT scan are on the right-side labeled in d), e) and f) with respect to the previous marking. The samples (diameter 2 mm) were cut from the middle of the original electrode area. SEM-secondary electrons (always left side of the image). Blue arrows show the contact of the GF fiber with the conductive phase of $BP_{ext.}$. SEM working conditions: 20 kV; MAG 1380x; VF 500 μ m. μ CT working conditions: Accelerating voltage of 55 kV, 2400 images/scan, resolution of 1.091 μ m/pixel, an exposure time of 6 s/image.

for the higher ASR_{dry} of the GF/ $BP_{ext.}$ even though the ASR_{dry} of this assembly was lower in the previous characterization arrangement (GF/ $BP_{ext.}$ measurement).

The overview of $ASR_{dry-cell}$ is in Table S1. We can see that the heat bonding of GF to the $BP_{ext.}$ led to the decrease of dry resistance by more than half (from 2.1 to 0.9 Ω cm^2). VRFB single-cell without membrane and with $BP_{com.}$ and with the CC/ BP / GF electrode assembly had the lowest $ASR_{dry-cell}$ among all the tested assemblies. If we compare these dry resistance values for $BP_{com.}$ and CC/ BP / GF with the ASR_{Ω} evaluated from EIS in 50 % SOC (see **chapter 3.2.3**), we can see that the resistance of the anion-exchange membrane used (FAP-450) creates about 1 Ω cm^2 from the overall single-cell ASR_{Ω} of approx. 1.5 Ω cm^2 .

3.2. Electrochemical testing of the electrode assemblies

This section presents the results of our complex electrochemical characterization of the manufactured electrode assemblies in a lab-scale VRFB in both single-cell and 2-cells stack set-up. These results are compared to a conventional VRFB cell and stack comprising $BP_{com.}$

without the heat-bonding. Based on dry resistance measurements (see previous section) for VRFB with unbonded GFs we used 20 % CR of GF, while for the VRFB with the bonded electrode assemblies we used only 10 % CR of GF. It's important to note that the Zahner device used for single-cell measurements had a cell connected with unshielded cables, which negatively affected the quality of the obtained EIS spectra (due to high contribution of inductance). Therefore, for single-cell measurements (except for the measurement with the developed $BP_{ext.}$ without HPW), mainly ASR_{LC} values and parameters evaluated from galvanostatic cycling are discussed. For the stack characterization, EIS and LC were measured for each cell separately (and for the stack as a whole), thus the information about ASR_{Ω} and ASR_{CT} from EIS will be discussed more in the stack results chapter.

Due to the gradual initial stabilization of the battery performance caused by membrane swelling and initially fast deactivation of the felt electrodes), only the $ASRs$ after the charge-discharge cycling are discussed. The initial $ASRs$ evaluated from EIS and load curve characterizations are shown in the supplementary (Figure S8–S10).

Fig. 6. Development of ASR_{dry} at various CRs of the felt for electrode assemblies: a) developed GF/BP_{ext.} and reference GF+BP_{com.}; b) developed GF/BP_{ext./GF} and reference GF+BP_{com.+GF} and GF+BP_{ext.+GF}, c) developed CC/BP_{ext./GF} and references CC+BP_{com.+GF} and CC+GF/BP_{ext.}. The sign “+” is used for unbonded components.

3.2.1. Electrochemical characterization in a VRFB single-cell

Fig. 7a shows the comparison of voltage profile in the last charge/discharge cycle of the single-cell at a current density of 40 mA cm^{-2} for four VRFB single-cell set-ups using the following assemblies: BP_{com.} (20 % CR); BP_{ext.} unbonded (20 % CR); BP_{ext.} with bonded GF/BP_{ext.} (10 % CR); BP_{ext.} with bonded CC/BP_{ext./GF} (10 % CR). In accordance with dry measurements the cell with the unbonded BP_{ext.} provided significantly higher voltage plateau separation, resulting in lower EE and CU (see Fig. 7c) due to its higher ASR_{Ω} . The polymer content in the BP_{ext.} is by 26 % higher than in the BP_{com.}, resulting in high resistance of the BP and BP-GF interface and thus high ASR_{LC} of the cell ($> 3 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$). As shown in Fig. 7b, the cell resistance significantly decreased when the BP_{ext.} was bonded with GF (ASR_{LC} decreased by $2 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$, compared to GF+BP_{ext.} assembly), resulting in increased EE by 9.7 % and CU by 14.2 %. The improved overall performance of the VRFB cell with GF/BP_{ext.} assembly is comparable with BP_{com.}, even at a lower CR of GFs (EE and CU of the commercial cell are only 1.4 % and 1.6 % higher, respectively, due to lower ASR_{LC} by $1 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$).

For the CC/BP_{ext./GF} electrode assembly, the ASR_{LC} of the single-cell is fully comparable with the cell based on BP_{com.}, providing an even higher EE by 1.7 %. This improvement is clearly related to the reduced contact resistance between CC and BP due to heat-bonding of the components. Importantly, the developed assemblies were tested at lower CRs of the GFs (by 10 %) than the reference cell, therefore enabling lower pressure drops and thus lower pumping losses, based on the study by [28]. For all four single-cell arrangements, CE values were around 98 % and remained stable throughout the cycling, which indicates that the

HPW did not negatively affected the selectivity of GF electrode reactions. To ensure consistency we have repeated measurements for selected electrode assemblies; GF/BP_{ext.} and CC/BP_{ext./GF} in VRFB single-cell. The results (see Table S2) of shows that there is no significant difference between two measurements.

3.2.2. Electrochemical characterization of microwave welded electrode assembly in a VRFB single-cell

Different GF (GF₂) was used for electrode assembly preparation via MWW and its comparison with the HPW method. VRFB single-cells with three different electrode arrangements were tested: a cell with: unbonded BP_{com.}, hot-press welded GF/BP_{ext.} and a microwave welded GF/BP_{ext.} electrode assembly. In Fig. 8a, a comparison of voltage profiles during the last charge/discharge galvanostatic cycle at 40 mA cm^{-2} shows that the cell polarization of all three set-ups is similar, which is in agreement with the ASR_{LC} values shown in Fig. 8b. The best performance (86 % EE and 79 % CU) was observed for the reference cell with BP_{com.}, the cell with microwave-welded GF/BP_{ext.} had EE lower by 1.26 % at the same CU . The hot-press welded GF/BP_{ext.} The electrode assembly provided decreased EE by 1.76 % with slightly lower CU (by 1.14 %), possibly due to a minor electrolyte leakage (approx. 2 ml) at the tubing connection during the battery cycling. The CE is around 98.5 % for all three cell set-ups, indicating that GF bonding did not affect the selectivity of electrode reactions in this case either.. In general, the performance of a VRFB single-cell with the electrode assemblies prepared by both welding methods was stable and comparable to the reference cell with the unbonded BP_{com.} (again, even at reduced CR of

Fig. 7. Summary of the VRFB single-cell experiment results: **a)** comparison of voltage profiles for galvanostatic cycling (last cycle); **b)** ASR_{LC} in +50 % SoC evaluated from load curve measurements. **c)** Mean values of (from 10 cycles) coulombic and energy efficiency and capacity utilization. **Electrodes assemblies:** BP_{ext.} (unbonded), BP_{com.} (unbonded), BP_{ext.} with bonded GF/BP_{ext.} assembly and BP_{ext.} with bonded CC/BP_{ext.}/GF assembly. **Working conditions:** 1.6 mol dm⁻³ vanadium electrolyte, room temperature, 75 ml min⁻¹, charge/discharge current density 40 mA cm⁻², voltage limits 0.8 V – 1.65 V. Load curve measurement current density range 0 – 60 mA cm⁻².}

Fig. 8. Summary of the VRFB single cell experiments results for two different welding methods of the GF-BP interface: **a)** voltage profile of last charge/discharge cycle, **b)** ASR_{LC} in 50 % SoC evaluated from load curve measurements for the three VRFB set-ups. **c)** Mean values of (from 10 cycles) coulombic and energy efficiency and capacity utilization. **Electrode assemblies:** for BP_{com.} (unbonded) and BP_{ext.} (bonded by HPW and MWW). **Working conditions:** 1.6 mol dm⁻³ vanadium electrolyte, room temperature, 75 ml min⁻¹, charge/discharge current density 40 mA cm⁻², voltage limits 0.8 V – 1.65 V. Load curve measurement current density range 0 – 60 mA cm⁻².

GF by 10 % for the bonded assemblies).

3.2.3. Electrochemical characterization of hot-pressed assemblies in VRFB stack

Finally, the prepared electrode assemblies based on BP_{ext.} were characterized in a 2-cell VRFB stack for three different electrode arrangements: a stack with unbonded BP_{com.} terminal electrodes (CC+BP_{com.}+GF), stack with partially bonded terminal electrode assemblies (CC+BP_{ext./GF}), and stack with fully bonded terminal electrode assemblies (CC/BP_{ext./GF}). Both latter stacks used middle bipolar GF/BP_{ext./GF} bonded electrode assembly (for stack arrangements see Table 6).

In Fig. 9d, the distribution of resistances in the stack is shown for all three stack set-ups. The major share of overall cell resistance evaluated from EIS spectra ($ASR_{EIS-tot}$) is created by ASR_{Ω} . The dominant share of ASR_{Ω} on $ASR_{EIS-tot}$ is the same for all three stack set-ups. It is probably due to the relatively thick membrane (50 μm) and its low ion exchange capacity IEC (0.93 meq g^{-1} [45]) required for prevention of vanadium ion cross-over. This was confirmed by the $ASR_{dry-cell}$ measurement (see chapter 3.1.4), showing that the membrane is responsible for approx. 1 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ per cell (approx. 2/3 of ASR_{Ω}). Fig. 9d shows that the ASR_{CT} was around 0.56 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ per cell for all the stacks. Thus, no increase of ASR_{CT} was observed for electrode assemblies, which implies that the HPW (additional heat treatment) did not affect the charge transfer resistance. The stacks using CC+GF/BP_{ext.} electrode assembly (i.e., without heat-bonding of CC) exhibited the highest $ASR_{EIS-tot}$ among the tested arrangements (approx. 2.9 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ per cell), due to high CC-BP_{ext.} interfacial resistance, which corresponds to the results of the single cell characterization. The stack with BP_{com.} had the lowest $ASR_{EIS-tot}$ (2 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ per cell), followed by the stack with CC/BP_{ext./GF} electrode assembly with a slight increase of $ASR_{EIS-tot}$ (by 0.1 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ per cell). The difference between the reference stack with BP_{com.} and developed a stack with CC/BP_{ext./GF} terminal electrode assemblies is thus comparable with the corresponding results of a single-cell experiment. The $ASR_{EIS-tot}$ and ASR_{LC} did not differ by > 5 %.

The lowest ASR_{Ω} of the reference stack with BP_{com.} are also reflected in the cycling parameters (see Fig. 9b), EE of 88.3 % was even higher when compared to the reference single-cell experiment (86.0 %), most probably due to the absence of BP-CC contact resistance in the middle bipolar electrode. Interestingly, CU of the reference stack decreased with the highest slope among the stack experiments of 1.1 % $Q_{theor.}$ per cycle. This is most probably due to achieving high SoC during charging, which increased the driving force for vanadium ion cross-over. The stack with CC+GF/BP_{ext.} terminal electrode assemblies, on the other hand, provided the lowest performance among the tested stacks, with the results corresponding to CC+GF/BP_{ext.} single-cell experiment (with only slightly higher EE by 0.72 % at the same CU). In contrast, the stack with CC/BP_{ext./GF} fully bonded terminal electrode assemblies had only slightly lower EE (by 1.39 %) and CU (by 1.89 %) than the reference stack (with BP_{com.}). This emphasizes the need for heat-bonding of the CC-BP interface for the BP_{ext.} with lower conductivity.

Closer analysis of the results brings an interesting observation: the stack with the CC/BP_{ext./GF} terminal assemblies initially provided lower EE and CU , which gradually increased over cycling. This trend was not observed in any other experiment. By the end of the cycling experiment, the polarization (also EE) of the stack was almost identical to that of the reference stack with unbonded BP_{com.} (see Fig. 9a). The lower initial efficiency was due to higher initial ASR_{Ω} (2 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ per cell, see

Figure S10b) which decreased throughout the cycling experiment (as shown by the increasing EE , CU , see Fig. 9b). Since only ASR_{Ω} decreased over time, while the change of ASR_{CT} was comparable with other measurements, the higher initial ASR_{Ω} is most likely due to slower activation of the membranes in this particular stack (due to the membrane swelling in the electrolyte). The membranes for all the experiments were from the same batch and a new membrane was always used for each experiment in the same way (assembled in a dry as received state). After the performance stabilization within the charge-discharge cycling, the ASR_{Ω} of the stack (with CC/BP_{ext./GF} electrode assemblies) was comparable to the BP_{com.} and proportional to a single-cell experiment.

To study the stability of the electrode assembly under accelerated VRFB working conditions, a long-term experiment was conducted, comprising over 800 cycles. The 2-cell VRFB stack consisted of a couple of terminal electrodes with integrated CC and GF, and a middle (bipolar) electrode assembly. Over 820 cycles, the mean CE was above 98.6 %, while achieving a mean EE of 61 % at double the current density compared to standard conditions. Figure S11a) illustrates the evolution of efficiencies and capacity utilization during the cycling. A gradual decrease in EE , caused most probably by deactivation of GF₂, which was also observed in previous experiments, was manifested by a significant increase in area-specific charge transfer resistance (ASR_{CT}) (see Figure S11b). Electrolytes were periodically remixed to restore the capacity that was continuously lost due to the electrolyte constituent cross-over through the membrane. After the series of cycling (comprising 4 electrolyte remixes), the used electrolyte was replaced with a fresh electrolyte to characterize the VRFB stack after the long-term experiment with electrolyte of initial composition. From the EIS measurement at 50 % SOC, it can be seen that the semicircle that represents ASR_{CT} increased significantly but the ohmic resistance increased only slightly, which suggests that more attention should be paid to the GF activation, but HPW presents a suitable manufacturing process for the electrode assemblies. To observe whether there is any structural damage of the electrode assembly, the electrode assemblies were characterized by microstructural analysis by SEM and μCT (see Fig. 5c and f). We did not observe any notable damage to the GF/BP interface. Thus, we have concluded that the stability of electrode assemblies is satisfactory even upon long-term cycling.

3.3. Discussion of the achieved results

In our study, the extruded weldable BP material with relatively high polymer content was used, which allowed us to heat-bond with GF by both selected welding methods and with CC using HPW. The production of BPs through a continuous extrusion process is easily scalable and suitable for large-scale production, leading to significant price reductions. The cost and material savings BP_{ext.} are attributed to two factors: reduced thickness (resulting in material savings) and a higher content of PP, which is approximately half the price of graphite. Even for small quantity quotation we estimate material cost reduction to be 30 % (see Table S5). Consequently, the cost reduction compared to standard compression-moulded BPs can be estimated at around 50–75 %, although this strongly depends on the scale. According to the price offers commercially available extruded BP (with high graphite filling and very limited available solutions) are approx. 40 % less expensive. Moreover, the BP_{ext.} is more flexible, considerably thinner and lighter, which also reduces the overall weight of the stack (i.e. transportation expenses). The connection of the GF electrode to the BP_{ext.} significantly reduces ASR_{Ω} by mitigating the contact resistance at the GF-BP interface and thus significantly increases overall performance to a level comparable with BP_{com.} (at higher CR). According to Charvat et al. [28] the pumping losses (pressure drop) increased by 18 % for PAN-based felt (at the same electrolyte velocity) when the CR increased from 10 % to 20 %, due to the decreased permeability of GF. Thus, the overall battery efficiency (including pumping losses) can be expected to be improved for the VRFB stack with the developed electrode assemblies. Connection of CC led to

Table 6
VRFB stack arrangements tested within the study.

Stack	Terminal electrode	Middle electrode
BP _{com.}	CC+BP _{com.} +GF	GF+BP _{com.} +GF
GF/BP _{ext.}	CC+GF/BP _{ext.}	GF/BP _{ext./GF}
CC/BP _{ext./GF}	CC/BP _{ext./GF}	GF/BP _{ext./GF}

Fig. 9. Summary of VRFB stack experiments results: a) Comparison of the last charge/discharge cycle in the VRFB stack with different electrode assemblies. b) Development of efficiencies and capacity utilization for the individual stack arrangements c) ASR_{LC} per cell in +50 % SoC evaluated from load curve measurements. d) ASR_{Ω} , ASR_{CT} , $ASR_{EIS-tot}$ per cell in 50 % SoC evaluated from EIS measurements. e) Mean values (from 10 cycles) of efficiencies and capacity utilization for the individual stack set-ups. Electrodes assemblies: for the reference stack with BP_{com.} and the developed stacks with CC+GF/BP_{ext.} and CC/BP_{ext.}/GF terminal electrode assemblies (using GF/BP_{ext.}/GF middle electrode assembly). Working conditions: 1.6 mol dm⁻³ vanadium electrolyte, room temperature, 150 ml min⁻¹, current density of 40 mA cm⁻², voltage limits 1.6 V - 3.3 V. Load curve measurement current density range 0 – 60 mA cm⁻².}}

the decrease of ASR_{Ω} , but more importantly, improved the homogeneity of current distribution, which is the main function of CC in RFB stacks. Both hot-press and microwave welding methods were successfully demonstrated. Welding of GF directly to the BP_{ext.} without any additional compounds (like ACL) prevents any possible contamination by different substances. Both methods offer similar welding quality, based on microstructure analysis and battery characterization. In this manuscript, both welding methods are batch processes. HPW parameters and principles can be adapted to a continuous roll-to-roll process, combining the extrusion of BP followed by GF welding using a Meyer machine [46].

This would result in a fully automated process with excellent scalability and significant cost reduction. MWW demonstrated significant time and power savings even at the current prototype scale. Implementing additional probes could further increase speed, and MWW could also be deployed in a roll-to-roll process following BP extrusion. However, additional research with different MWW equipment is needed to confirm the feasibility of welding GF from both sides. According to Noack et al. [47] stack price is 40 % of the overall VRFB system, while the electrodes stand for approx. one third of the stack price. They showed that BP with better mechanical properties and lower price would be more

advantageous despite its lower conductivity. Our developed electrode assemblies achieved comparable parameters to conventional assembly and, in combination with all that was mentioned, the LCOS of VRFB can be significantly decreased. Some more detailed discussion of techno-economical aspects of this study is provided in SI. Nevertheless, it must be pointed out, that detailed techno-economic analysis would require access to specific production scales and suitable tooling, which are beyond the scope of this study.

The highest share of ASR_{Ω} for the cells and stacks tested within this study was created by the anion-exchange membrane used, due to their relatively high thickness (50 μm) and low IEC (0.93 meq g^{-1} [45]) required for low vanadium ion permeability. This was confirmed by $ASR_{\text{dry-cell}}$ measurements (for a single-cell without electrolytes and membrane, as shown in Section 3.1.4). The higher resistance of membranes, along with high ASR of unbonded $\text{BP}_{\text{ext.}}$, led us to the choice of a relatively low current density for galvanostatic cycling of 40 mA cm^{-2} .

Lim et al. [38] presented HPW of the GF and their own compression-moulded BPs (PE was used as polymer binder). They demonstrated that electrode assembly at low compression of GF has significantly lower ASR when compared to the conventional assembly and the difference is mitigated when the pressure is higher, due to the reduced contact resistance. This is in accordance with our findings. Unfortunately, the experimental conditions of VRFB testing are not sufficiently described (e.g., current density), thus relevant comparison of archived parameters is not possible.

Similarly, Choe and Lim [39] reported that the HPW of CC to the BP increased EE by 1.9 % (to 82.4 % at 100 mA cm^{-2}) when compared to a conventional assembled VRFB single-cell with the composite BP (composed of a single layer of carbon/epoxy prepreg WSN 1k, both sides coated with a 100 μm -thick graphite layer), and by 4.1 % when compared to commercial BPs. The observed improvement is similar to the results obtained within our study. In the mentioned study, only CC was connected to BP via HPW using carbon/epoxy prepreg in-between the components with the hot-press manufacture time of 2 h. In contrast, in our study, no additional material was needed for the bonding and the preparation (including connection of GF) took approx. 30 min using the optimized HPW method.

Another comparison of our results can be made to the study by Kaur et al. [37], where the authors used a single piece of GF for the construction of a bipolar electrode, with an electrolyte impermeable middle plate created within the GF structure by application of low-viscous epoxy. This assembly was placed into the hot-press for 24 h to create the resulting bipolar electrode. The component resulted in a 28 % reduction of ASR_{dry} by eliminating a GF-BP contact resistance. When tested in a VRFB 2-cell stack, they achieved EE of 86.65 % at 50 mA cm^{-2} in the voltage range of 2.4–3.3 V. The experimental conditions and the resulting parameters are thus comparable to our study, despite using a broader voltage range 1.6–3.3 V (which, in general, decreases EE). However, the approach used in Kaur's study is only applicable for the middle electrode assemblies, while in our study, GFs were also heat-bonded within the terminal electrode assemblies, which makes direct result comparison difficult. Nevertheless, the preparation time in Kaur's study was >24 h, whereas, only about 20 min in our study using HPW. Reducing manufacturing time is necessary for further cost reduction of VRFB stack fabrication. Our study demonstrated that the HPW method is suitable for the fabrication of both terminal electrode assemblies (including integrating copper-based CC) and the middle bipolar electrode assemblies for RFB at a relatively high production rate. The performance in VRFB showed comparable results to unbonded commercial materials with potential for the reduced costs of stack fabrication.

4. Conclusions

In this contribution, we developed and studied heat-bonded electrode assemblies for RFB. Two types of terminal electrode assemblies

(GF/ $\text{BP}_{\text{ext.}}$ and CC/ $\text{BP}_{\text{ext.}}$ /GF) and one bipolar electrode assembly (GF/ $\text{BP}_{\text{ext.}}$ /GF) were successfully developed. This was enabled by the use of our own extruded BP with a rich polymer phase (40 wt. % of polypropylene) and systematic optimization of the bonding conditions. Two different manufacturing processes were successfully carried out, specifically hot-press welding and microwave welding for the bonding of GF to $\text{BP}_{\text{ext.}}$. Detailed micro-structure analysis (μCT and SEM) showed that there is no clear difference in the quality of the welds between the methods. The microwave welding allowed significantly faster production of electrode assemblies with similar parameters to hot-press welded ones. Both methods can be implemented in a continuous manufacturing process, which allows the large-scale, cost-effective electrode assemblies. The resistance of the developed electrode assemblies was characterized at a broad CR range under dry conditions, followed by complex characterization in VRFB single-cell and 2-cell stack. Both manufacturing processes led to the significant reduction of ASR_{Ω} by mitigating the contact resistances between the individual components (ASR_{Ω} decreased up to 2.5 times for single-cell experiments). The results of experiments with single-cell and stack showed comparable performance of the developed electrode assemblies with the corresponding arrangements based on commercial unbonded BPs. The total ASR of the VRFB stack with fully bonded terminal electrode assemblies was 2.1 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ (per cell) and the EE was 86.9 % at 40 mA cm^{-2} with significantly higher assay of polymer phase (40 %) in BP. The continuous production of $\text{BP}_{\text{ext.}}$ should enable a significant decrease of the production costs, this, together with the reduced number of components during the stack assembly, will decrease the overall costs of RFB stack production which can be easily adopted for various RFB electrolyte chemistries. Deployment of the continuous production will lead to additional cost reduction, while the reduction of the cost strongly depends on the production scale.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Přemysl Richtr: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Tobias Gerber:** Methodology, Investigation. **Peter Fischer:** Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Jiří Charvát:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Christian Röss:** Methodology, Investigation. **Jens Noack:** Conceptualization. **Björn Hage:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Miloš Svoboda:** Investigation. **David Gráf:** Visualization, Investigation. **Jan Beneš:** Investigation. **Petr Mazúr:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Přemysl Richtr reports financial support was provided by DAAD German Academic Exchange Service. Petr Mazur reports a relationship with Pinflow Energy Storage that includes: equity or stocks. Jiří Charvát reports a relationship with Pinflow Energy Storage that includes: employment. Peter Fischer has patent #EP3444884 B2 / DE102017007718 A1 licensed to FRAUNHOFER GES FORSCHUNG. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the project "The Energy Conversion and Storage", funded as project No CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research.

This work was supported by TAČR, program 1. VS THETA2, project no TS01030093.

This work was supported by the grant of Specific university research – grant A1_FCHI_2024_04 and A2_FCHI_2024_011.

This work (Přemysl Richtr) was supported by the DAAD exchange programme Research Grants - One-Year Grants for Doctoral Candidates, 2023/24 (57645447).

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.rineng.2025.106285](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2025.106285).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] European Commission. *2050 long-term strategy*. [cited 2022 Nov. 1]; Available from: https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/climate-strategies-targets/2050-long-term-strategy_en.
- [2] M. Laimon, Renewable energy curtailment: a problem or an opportunity? *Results Eng.* 26 (2025) 104925.
- [3] V. Mahadevan, et al., Critical review of energy storage systems: a comparative assessment of mechanisms, advantages, challenges, and integration with renewable energy, *Results Eng.* 26 (2025) 105589.
- [4] N. Sandia, Laboratories. DOE Global Energy Storage Database Projects, 2022 [cited 2022 Oct 25]; Available from: <https://sandia.gov/ess-ssl/gesdb/public/projects.html>.
- [5] W. Hill Balliet, et al., Determining the profitability of energy storage over its life cycle using leveled cost of storage, *Energy Econ.* 142 (2025) 108174.
- [6] E. Sánchez-Díez, et al., Redox flow batteries: status and perspective towards sustainable stationary energy storage, *J. Power Sources* 481 (2021) 228804.
- [7] K. Lourenssen, et al., Vanadium redox flow batteries: a comprehensive review, *J. Energy Storage* 25 (2019) 100844.
- [8] P. Mazur, et al., Effect of graphite felt properties on the long-term durability of negative electrode in vanadium redox flow battery, *J. Power Sources* 414 (2019) 354–365.
- [9] M. Skyllas-Kazacos, J.F. McCann, Chapter 10 - vanadium redox flow batteries (VRBs) for medium- and large-scale energy storage, in: C. Menictas, M. Skyllas-Kazacos, T.M. Lim (Eds.), *Advances in Batteries for Medium and Large-Scale Energy Storage*, Woodhead Publishing, 2015, pp. 329–386. Editors.
- [10] Á. Cunha, et al., Vanadium redox flow batteries: a technology review, *Int. J. Energy Res.* 39 (7) (2015) 889–918.
- [11] P. Leung, et al., Progress in redox flow batteries, remaining challenges and their applications in energy storage, *RSC Adv.* 2 (27) (2012) 10125–10156.
- [12] L. Gubler, Membranes and separators for redox flow batteries, *Curr. Opin. Electrochem.* 18 (2019) 31–36.
- [13] R.K. Gautam, A. Kumar, A review of bipolar plate materials and flow field designs in the all-vanadium redox flow battery, *J. Energy Storage* 48 (2022) 104003.
- [14] B. Caglar, et al., Conductive polymer composites and coated cetals as alternative bipolar plate materials for all-vanadium redox-flow batteries, *Adv. Mater. Lett.* 5 (6) (2014) 299–308.
- [15] C. Minke, et al., Cost and performance prospects for composite bipolar plates in fuel cells and redox flow batteries, *J. Power Sources* 305 (2016) 182–190.
- [16] B. Caglar, et al., Development of carbon nanotube and graphite filled polyphenylene sulfide based bipolar plates for all-vanadium redox flow batteries, *J. Power Sources* 256 (2014) 88–95.
- [17] Z. Huang, et al., Comprehensive analysis of critical issues in all-vanadium redox flow battery, *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* 10 (24) (2022) 7786–7810.
- [18] K.J. Kim, et al., A technology review of electrodes and reaction mechanisms in vanadium redox flow batteries, *J. Mater. Chem. A* 3 (33) (2015) 16913–16933.
- [19] P. Mazúr, et al., Performance evaluation of thermally treated graphite felt electrodes for vanadium redox flow battery and their four-point single cell characterization, *J. Power Sources* 380 (2018) 105–114.
- [20] B. Shanahan, et al., Rapid wet-chemical oxidative activation of graphite felt electrodes for vanadium redox flow batteries, *RSC Adv.* 11 (51) (2021) 32095–32105.
- [21] J.E. Barranco, et al., Analysis of the electrochemical performance of carbon felt electrodes for vanadium redox flow batteries, *Electrochim. Acta* 470 (2023) 143281.
- [22] R.K. Gautam, M. Kapoor, A. Verma, Tactical surface modification of a 3D graphite felt as an electrode of vanadium redox flow batteries with enhanced electrolyte utilization and fast reaction kinetics, *Energy Fuels* 34 (4) (2020) 5060–5071.
- [23] Y. Xiao, et al., Review and perspectives of the In situ modification strategy for bifunctional electrodes in a vanadium redox flow battery, *Energy Fuels* 38 (14) (2024) 12433–12446.
- [24] S. Zhong, et al., Comparison of the physical, chemical and electrochemical properties of rayon- and polyacrylonitrile-based graphite felt electrodes, *J. Power Sources* 45 (1) (1993) 29–41.
- [25] T.J. Rabbow, et al., Variability within a single type of polyacrylonitrile-based graphite felt after thermal treatment. Part II: chemical properties, *Electrochim. Acta* 173 (2015) 24–30.
- [26] Y. Jiang, et al., Maneuverable B-site cation in perovskite tuning anode reaction kinetics in vanadium redox flow batteries, *J. Mater. Sci. Technol.* 186 (2024) 199–206.
- [27] P. Mazur, et al., A complex four-point method for the evaluation of ohmic and faradaic losses within a redox flow battery single-cell, *MethodsX* 6 (2019) 534–539.
- [28] J. Charvát, et al., Performance enhancement of vanadium redox flow battery by optimized electrode compression and operational conditions, *J. Energy Storage* 30 (2020) 101468.
- [29] D. Maggiolo, et al., Particle based method and X-ray computed tomography for pore-scale flow characterization in VRFB electrodes, *Energy Storage Mater.* 16 (2019) 91–96.
- [30] J. Schneider, et al., Deconvolution of electrochemical impedance data for the monitoring of electrode degradation in VRFB, *Electrochim. Acta* 336 (2020) 135510.
- [31] P.C. Ghimire, et al., A comprehensive study of electrode compression effects in all vanadium redox flow batteries including locally resolved measurements, *Appl. Energy* 230 (2018) 974–982.
- [32] C.-L. Hsieh, et al., Effect of compression ratio of graphite felts on the performance of an all-vanadium redox flow battery, *Energies* 12 (2) (2019) 313.
- [33] L.D. Brown, et al., The effect of felt compression on the performance and pressure drop of all-vanadium redox flow batteries, *J. Energy Storage* 8 (2016) 91–98.
- [34] K.I. Jeong, et al., An integrated composite structure with reduced electrode /bipolar plate contact resistance for vanadium redox flow battery, *Compos. B: Eng.* 233 (2022) 109657.
- [35] S.-K. Park, et al., The influence of compressed carbon felt electrodes on the performance of a vanadium redox flow battery, *Electrochim. Acta* 116 (2014) 447–452.
- [36] J. Cao, et al., A promising assembled electrode-bipolar plate for redox flow battery, *J. Energy Storage* 97 (2024) 112936.
- [37] A. Kaur, S.S. Kim, J.W. Lim, Electrode-integrated bipolar plate structure for multi-cells in vanadium redox flow batteries, *J. Power Sources* 598 (2024) 234188.
- [38] J.W. Lim, D.G. Lee, Carbon fiber/polyethylene bipolar plate-carbon felt electrode assembly for vanadium redox flow batteries (VRFB), *Compos. Struct.* 134 (2015) 483–492.
- [39] J. Choe, J.W. Lim, Carbon-composite bipolar plate-integrated current collector for vanadium redox flow battery, *J. Power Sources* 589 (2024) 233751.
- [40] Fischer, P., et al., *Electrically conductive contact plate for electrochemical cells, electrochemical cells with such contact plate and method for the production thereof*, in https://worldwide.espacenet.com/publicationDetails/biblio?DB=EPODOC&II=0&ND=3&adjacent=true&locale=en_EP&FT=D&date=20190221&CC=DE&NR=102017007718A1&KC=A1#. 2019: Germany.
- [41] M. Hala, et al., Characterization of commercial polymer-carbon composite bipolar plates used in PEM fuel cells, *Membranes* 12 (11) (2022) 1050.
- [42] Eisenhuth GmbH & Co. KG. *PPG86 - Technical data sheet*. 2024 [cited 2025 May 26]; Available from: <https://eisenhuth.de/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/PPG86-ENGLISH.pdf>.
- [43] D.S. Sahota, A. Bansal, V. Kumar, Application of microwave in welding of metallic materials – a review, *Mater. Today: Proc.* 43 (2021) 466–470.
- [44] H. Sadeghifar, N. Djalili, M. Bahrami, Thermal conductivity of a graphite bipolar plate (BPP) and its thermal contact resistance with fuel cell gas diffusion layers: effect of compression, PTFE, micro porous layer (MPL), BPP out-of-flatness and cyclic load, *J. Power Sources* 273 (2015) 96–104.
- [45] T. Wang, et al., Poly(terphenylene) anion exchange membranes with high conductivity and low vanadium permeability for vanadium redox flow batteries (VRFBs), *J. Membr. Sci.* 598 (2020) 117665.
- [46] Meyer Machines. *Meyer Machines Applications*. 2025 [cited 2025 May 26]; Available from: <https://meyer-machines.com/en/applications/>.
- [47] J. Noack, et al., Techno-economic modeling and analysis of redox flow battery systems, *Energies* 9 (8) (2016) 627.